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Annotation: In this article, the history of the development of status art and its development today, issues such as studying it and teaching status art to the younger generation today, attention to status art and status in Uzbekistan Information about the measures being implemented for the development of art, "Maqom Festival" held in Shahrisabz city.

Key words: Maqom, national art, music, Shashmaqom, methods, prose, weight, melody, Maqom festival, Maqom conference.

If we want to know and learn the original, true art, we must first know and learn the art of classical status. If we want to promote art and culture, we must first promote the art of classical status.

We need to mobilize all our capabilities so that the melodies, spirit and philosophy of Maqam take a deep place in the hearts of every person, first of all, in the minds and hearts of our young generation.

The tone that leaked out of the status of our people. Maqam is derived from the Arabic language and means place, space, place, level, address. Its main musical term is related to the meaning of "the place where musical sound is produced in musical instruments", i.e. curtain. Many other aspects of the content are also directly related to these curtains. Maqam is a complex of instrumental melodies and chants created by the combination of perfect curtain association and circle techniques. One of the main concepts in the music of the Muslim East. The art of maqam has a centuries-old history and is an example of professional music that is passed down from generation to generation through the "master-disciple" tradition. Initially, it was used in the sense of a fret, a place on the handle of a stringed instrument to be pressed with a finger to produce a sound of a certain pitch. Later, in the course of the development of Eastern music theory, the scope of Maqam expanded and began to mean other related meanings: chord structure, chord system; melodies created on the ground of certain curtains; form, genre; single-part or ensemble instrumental and vocal tracks; musical style and other theoretical and musical aesthetic issues related to Maqam Abu Yusuf Yaqub ibn Ishaq al-Kindi and Farabi (IX-X century), Ibn Sina and Ibn Zayla (XI century), Safiuddin al-Urmawi (XIII century), Mahmud ash- He researched in the musical treatises of Shirozi and Abdulkadir Maroghi (XIV century), Jami and Zainulobiddin Husayni (XV century), Najmiddin Kavkabi Bukhari (XVI century), Darvishali Changi (XVII century) and other scholars. In Near and Middle Eastern classical music theory, the number of Maqams was not clearly defined until the 13th century. Safiuddin al-Urmawi scientifically classified the veil structures in the names of maqam and developed the twelve maqam system. This system was used until the 17th century with some improvements. On the basis of the twelve maqam, various national and regional maqam types and categories were later created. These are pronounced as "Maqom" in Uzbeks and Tajiks, "Murom" or "Dastgoh" in Turkmen, Azerbaijani and Armenians, "Makam" in Turks, and "Maqam" in Arab nations. The maqams are a very good example of art in terms of form and structure. Therefore, many thinkers who lived and worked in the past, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Sayfiddin Urmawi, Qutbiddin Shirozi, Abdurakhman

Jami and others wrote scientific treatises on status. In this way, the science of status performance, creativity and status theory was developed. There are 3 types of statuses in Uzbekistan, they are named as follows:

1. Six statuses (Shashmaqom or Bukhara statuses)
2. Statuses of Khorezm
3. Fergana - Tashkent authorities.

Shashmaqom was expressed in Bukhara in the middle of the 18th century by court professional musicians and musicologists in the form of a series consisting of Six Maqoms. Shashmaqom means the association of six perfect curtains. Shashmaqom consists of the following six statuses:

1. Buzruk - "Big, great, great"
2. True - "True, true"
3. Navo - "Song, sad tune"
4. Dugoh - "Two places, two places"
5. Segoh - "Three seats, three curtains"
6. Iraq is an Arab country.

Shashmaqom was created as a product of past compositional traditions, based on rich experience in makom making. Over the next two centuries, in the course of oral transmission from one musician - singer to another, Shashmaqom underwent great changes and has reached us. This is clearly noticeable when comparing the names of maqam and branches in the collections of poems composed in the XIX century and attributed to maqam, the measures of the poem with the parts of the current maqam. Shashmaqom is the basis of folk music heritage. It contains about 250 instrumental and vocal tracks. If we take into account the hundreds of samples of folk tunes and songs created on the basis of them, we can once again find out how important the role of maqam is in folk music. Shashmaqom means six positions in Tajik.

Buzruk, rost, navo, dugoh, segoh, and iraq maqams in shashmaqom are each large-scale serial works, containing 20 to 45 large and small maqam tracks. In the past, tanbur and दौरا were considered leading words in the performance of statuses. The parts of maqam are performed in the style of a series or in the style of single tunes and chants by a soloist, a singer or a group. The choir consisted of two tanburs, one dutor, one qubuz or sato, a circle and several singers.

The art of maqam is present in the musical heritage of most eastern nations and forms the basis of national music. Maqams are a series of musical ensembles created in a certain order, and are a unique and polished type of compositional creativity. Maqams is a community of folk music in a broad sense. Because in them, in particular, in Shashmaqom, a number of aspects based on the weight characteristics, tones, circle methods, and the rules of connection of poetry and folk songs found their full expression in the music of the Uzbek and Tajik peoples. Ghiyosuddin, the author of "Iyasul - Lug'at", defines it as follows: "Maqom - pardai surudro goyand" - "Maqom is said to the curtain of tunes and songs."

Maqam is the tone that has leaked from the body of our people. Therefore, it has been living for centuries. Even today, great attention is paid to the art of Maqom. As the head of state stated in the meeting with the representatives of the creative intellectuals of Uzbekistan: "We will widely promote the art of status, which is a unique heritage of our people, not only in our country, but throughout the world, and if necessary, hold status competitions on an international scale. We need to work on organization," they said. Also, on November 17, 2017, by President Shavkat

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Mirziyoyev No. 3391 "On the further development of Uzbek national status art and the use of the wide possibilities of status art to educate young people in the spirit of high human feelings, to form their aesthetic taste and thinking" decision was made. This document is excellent in studying the art of Uzbek status in depth, developing its unique performing schools and traditions at a new stage, creating and enriching its "Golden Fund", increasing its international prestige and widely promoting it. is important. The endless attention paid to the development of the art of national status gives inspiration and pleasure to all artists. The Uzbek people have a huge and unique musical heritage. "Shashmaqom" and its series, which is considered to be the masterpiece of Uzbek national music art, created a beautiful example of art in harmony with our classical poetry, and people of the world look at this high music with admiration.

Based on the decision made in 2017, the National Art Center of Uzbekistan was established. The main goal of the center is to further develop the art of Uzbek national status, the traditions of performance and creative schools formed in this regard, the heritage of great hafiz, composers and musicians on a deep scientific basis, to study and restore, promote, and promote the musical heritage of our nation. It consists of tasks such as enjoying the most beautiful traditions, developing a sense of national identity in the young generation by introducing them to the art of status.

The decision of the President of April 6, 2018 "On holding the international status art conference" was accepted. According to the decision, in the area of Oksaroy Square in Shahrisabz, various exhibitions related to status art, national songs and costumes, handicrafts, works of visual and applied art, examples of sculpture, feature and documentary films, books, albums will be displayed and sold. was put on. According to the President's decision, the First International Art Conference will be held in the historical center of Shahrisabz on September 6-10, 2018. About 300 solo singers from 75 countries of the world, representatives of the diplomatic corps of folklore groups took part in this conference. 30 musicologists from 19 countries participated in the international scientific-practical conference held as part of the conference. A special amphitheater with 1,800 seats, built for guests and hosts, held concerts in the Oksaroy area. On September 6, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev gave a speech at the opening ceremony of the International Status Art Conference in Shahrisabz. In his speech: "Shashmaqom" which is a product of the artistic thinking of our people, i.e. six statuses, so to speak, can be compared to six rivers. These rivers have been pouring into the ocean of world culture for centuries, filling and enriching it in every way. That is why it is deeply meaningful and important that this great musical masterpiece was included in the list of World Cultural Heritage by UNESCO. On September 10, in the amphitheater on Oksaroy Square, which has become the main stage of the world's artists, the awarding ceremony of the winners of the International Status Art Conference was held. passed. The international jury evaluated the performances of the participants in three categories: "Best Status Ensemble", "Best Solo Instrumentalist" and "Best Solo Singer". The Second International Status Art Conference was held on September 5-10, 2020. "During the past period, certain works have been carried out in our country to study and develop the art of status. In particular, the publication of the sheet music of the Uzbek "Shashmaqom" and the corresponding recording of the songs on magnetic tapes was an event of great scientific and cultural importance.

In short, Maqom art serves to educate young people in the spirit of high human feelings, to form their aesthetic taste and thinking. It opens the door to wide opportunities in realizing our national identity and improving our culture in all aspects. The Maqom conference, which is held

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every 2 years, provides an opportunity to convey our great national cultural heritage to the peoples of the world and to get acquainted with their national music.

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